

Studies on Adsorption of Anils by Silica, Alumina, Aluminium Silicate, Ferric Silicate and Aluminium Molybdate Gels from Non Polar Solvents

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The adsorption of phenacylidene aniline, *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenyl glyoxal and *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenyl glyoxal nitrile on polar adsorbents silica, alumina, aluminium silicate, ferric silicate and aluminium molybdate from nonpolar solvents benzene, xylene, toluene, carbontetrachloride and dioxane has been studied at various concentrations and at 30°.

It has been found that the isotherms obey Langmuir equation and the order of adsorption is in the following order :

p-dimethyl amino anil of phenyl glyoxal nitrile > *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenyl glyoxal > phenacylidene aniline from all the solvents.

Numerous examples of constitutive influences in adsorption have been pointed out by various workers¹⁻⁶. Their investigations show that the nature and arrangement of atoms or groups in the molecule affect the adsorption phenomenon. In certain cases the possibility of the molecular orientation during adsorption has also been indicated.

From the point of view of constitutive influences, the class of compounds known as anils have not been studied so far. These compounds undergo complex ion formation with Lewis acids due to bathochromic effect⁷ present in them. They also develop blue violet colour on silica gel from their solution in benzene, but how this change in colour takes place is yet to be investigated.

The present paper deals with the adsorption of anils of phenyl glyoxal and phenyl glyoxal nitrile on a number of inorganic gels namely silica, alumina, aluminium silicate etc., in the non polar solvents.

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EXPERIMENTAL

1. *Materials*

(a) *Adsorbents* :—(i) Silica⁸⁻¹⁰, (ii) Alumina¹¹⁻¹³, (iii) Aluminium silicate¹⁴, (iv) Ferric silicate¹⁵ and Aluminium molybdate¹⁶ gels were prepared by the usual methods. They were activated by heating upto $300^{\circ} \pm 10^{\circ}$ in a muffle furnace, cooled and stored in a well closed bottle.

(b) *Solvents* :—All chemicals used were from B.D.H. The solvents (benzene, xylene, toluene, carbontetrachloride and dioxane) were purified¹⁷ by standard methods and obtained free from moisture.

(c) *Adsorbates* :—Stock solutions of different anils, viz., phenacylidene aniline¹⁸, *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenylglyoxal and *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenylglyoxal nitrile¹⁹ were prepared by dissolving purified product in the different solvents. It was found that the Beer's law was fairly applicable to the concentrations at which study was made.

2. *Apparatus and Technique*

Bausch and Lomb 'Spectronic 20' was used for absorption measurements.

Procedure :—To study the adsorption of anils 25.0 ml. solution of the known concentration of anils were taken in several 100 ml. flasks containing 1.0 g. of gel. The flasks were fixed on a shaker fitted in an air thermostat and shaken well for 6 hr. at a constant temperature of $30^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$ to attain equilibrium. Then the mixtures were allowed to remain at the same temperature in the thermostat for the next 18 hr. The supernatant liquids were taken out, centrifuged to allow the gel settle and concentration of anils in the supernatant liquid determined spectrophotometrically. The wave lengths used were 350, 425 and 525m μ respectively for phenacylidene aniline, *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenylglyoxal and *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenylglyoxal nitrile and the adsorption was calculated.

Curves were plotted between equilibrium concentration (CS) and the millimoles of anil adsorbed per gm (x/m) of the adsorbent.

Surface area of adsorbents : The surface areas of the gel powders were determined by adsorbing PNP from water²⁰ at pH 10.0.

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Density and porosity : Density measurements (true D_t and bulk D_b) were made by using benzene and mercury as displacement liquids²¹. Pore volume of gels were obtained from the equation.

$$V_p (1/D_b - 1/D_t)$$

Surface area and porevolume of different gels are tabulated below :

TABLE I

Gel	Surface area m ² /g	Pore volume
Silica	700	0.70
Alumina	614	0.50
Al-Silicate	560	0.90
Fe-silicate	500	0.43
Al-molybdate	480	0.60

Desorption and reversibility : A set of experiments was designed to see if the anils adsorption process was truly reversible. It consisted of adsorbing anils solution in benzene, xylene, toluene, carbontetrachloride and dioxane on to silica, alumina, Al-silicate, Fe-silicate and Al-molybdate gels at room temperature, decanting as much of the excess solution as possible, adding some pure solvent, and desorbing by agitating the gel and solvent slurry. The desorbing solvents used were benzene, xylene, toluene, carbontetrachloride, dioxane, chloroform, ethylalcohol, methylalcohol, acetone, ethyl-acetate and acetonitrile. In non-polar solvent desorption was slow and complete in few hours. Desorption with polar solvent was quick and complete in one to two hours. This shows the physical adsorption of the anils.

The values of average particle diameters are calculated from the surface area (A) and the reciprocal of the real density of the gel and are reported in Table II. These values give close approximations to the true average dimensions of the particles.

TABLE II

Gels	Real density g/cc	Particle density g/cc	Pore vol. cc/g	Particle diameter A.U.	Average pore diameter A.U.
Silica	2.24	0.87	0.70	38	60
Alumina	2.16	1.03	0.50	45	48
Al-silicate	2.20	0.73	0.90	48	96
Fe-silicate	2.80	1.01	0.43	66	51
Al-molybdate	2.00	0.90	0.60	62	75

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Adsorption isotherms of phenacylidene aniline, *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenylglyoxal and *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenylglyoxal nitrile in a non polar solvent (carbontetrachloride) on samples of different gels are shown in Figs. 1-5 (isotherms in other solvents are not shown because of the same nature). It will be seen that the isotherms are practically of the same nature in all gels. Positive adsorption is detected with all the solutes and the rapidity of adsorption shows that it occurs only on the external surface of the particles²². The adsorption isotherms given in Figs. 1-5 show that the adsorption increases with increasing concentration of the anils. The adsorption isotherms are however regular and concave to the concentration axis. This suggests that the adsorption is possibly of unimolecular layer.

- 1 PHENACYLIDENE ANILINE
- × 2. *p*-DIMETHYL AMINO ANIL OF PHENYL GLYOXAL
- 3. *p*-DIMETHYL AMINO ANIL OF PHENYL GLYOXAL NITRILE

Much of the data in the literature in which a solute is adsorbed from solution on a solid adsorbent can be satisfactorily fitted to a Langmuir type equation indicating that the adsorption is monomolecular in nature. In the present experiments the adsorption of anils from all the nonpolar solvents on different inorganic gels appears to be essentially Langmuir in character and the order of adsorption is *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenylglyoxal nitrile > *p*-dimethyl amino anil of phenylglyoxal > phenacylidene aniline. The adsorption

affinities of the gels are in the order silica gel > alumina > Al-silicate > Fe-silicate < Al-molybdate. The presence of -CN and double bonds raises the adsorbability in the solute²³. The experimental results further suggest that adsorption increases as the mol. wt. increases. The Langmuir equation can be expressed in the form,

$$x/m = abc/(1/ac)$$

or

$$\frac{c}{(x/m)} = \frac{1}{ab} + \frac{c}{b}$$

In the above equation x/m is the amount adsorbed in moles per gm. and c is the eq. concentration. Straight lines were obtained when m/x was plotted against $1/cs$ indicating that the Langmuir equation provides a reasonable fit for these data.

FIG. 5

The extent of adsorption, however clearly varies considerably with the nature of the solvent. A possible interpretation would be that the orientation of the anils molecules at the surface varies according to the solvent from which it was adsorbed. Due to -OH groups present on the surface of the adsorbent, the structure of the anils might be changing from benzenoid to quinonoid form thereby developing colour.

Two observations support this :

(a) Coloured complexes are formed in the decreasing strength in the order silica, alumina, Al-silicate, Fe-silicate and Al-molybdate (no colour). The first two gels are having

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a high density of surface -OH groups²⁴ and the others which have these groups to a much less extent (silica 8-OH/100 A⁰², Alumina 6-OH/100 A⁰², Al-silicate 3-OH/100A⁰², Fe-silicate 2-OH/100 A⁰² and Al-molybdate-nil).

(b) The solvents (acetone, chloroform, acetonitrile, ethyl alcohol) which easily elute and complex are those which form strong bonds with surface -OH groups.

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